

Using Various Assessment and Feedback Tools for Teaching English at the Undergraduate Level in Bangladesh

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Abstract

This study focuses mainly on the use of different types of assessment and feedback towards the study of English language at graduation level in Bangladesh. Assessment and feedback are an important part of effective learning. Assessment should also be incorporated in the teaching and learning process. The current tendency in the Bangladeshi education system, assessment and feedback are largely focused on pedagogic characteristics, ignoring those that are relevant to the curriculum. The quantitative method has been used to collect data and includes students' perceptions, ideas, and behaviors. This research paper was developed with a questionnaire including teachers and students. From the data, the researcher finds that students face a lot of difficulty in getting the actual assessment and feedback. In most cases, students receive only verbal feedback from teachers. In addition, teachers are more interested in providing written feedback. This study also aims to provide suggestions for overcoming barriers to exam performance and feedback in teaching English language at the undergraduate level in Bangladesh.

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1. Introduction

Assessment and feedback are an integral part of English teaching and learning activities. It refers to the process used by the teacher's learning activities to improve student performance in assessment tasks. Practical assessment of language learning should be done by teachers in the classroom. Black & Wiliam mention that research, in fact, shows the powerful effect that on-going Assessment embedded into the learning process has on student learning, particularly for low ability students (1998). In addition, assessment for learning is the idea that classroom assessments should support ongoing teaching and learning (Assessment Reform Group, 2002; Heritage, 2010), thus highlighting the vital role that teacher-made classroom-based formative and process-focused assessments could play in improving the entire education system. The results of assessment and feedback may be negative or positive for students. These results have far-reaching effects and impact not only on students but also on teachers, the community and the entire educational environment. Therefore, the test needs to be done with the mind because it helps to see what works and what needs attention. At the foundation of education, assessment can be broadly defined as a continuous and ongoing effort to improve the quality of teaching, learning, and assessment and curriculum development. The purpose of this paper is to present a general overview of the research conducted in English language education at the graduate level in Bangladesh.

1.1 Objectives of the Study

The research tries to find out the common and popular assessment used in teaching English language at the undergraduate level in Bangladesh. It also investigates whether appropriate assessment and feedback are used to teach the learners. The outcomes of the research will bring out the real scenario of assessment and feedback on teaching English language. The research is supposed to provide suggestions for problems of assessment and feedback.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Bangladeshi learners learn English from their very beginning as a compulsory subject, most of them are not able to achieve the knowledge of English language fully. The problematic methodology is the main cause behind it. Effective assessments and feedback are not used in classrooms at all. Teachers are not aware to include appropriate assessment and to give feedback. Students are not able to understand the lectures of teachers. This is the main problem. Long-established assessments are always followed by teachers. It is important to find out whether appropriate activities and materials are being used to teach the learners in the classroom while teaching English language. The time duration for teaching English language learning is also not satisfactory.

1.3 Research Questions

The research questions of this study intend to find out the difficulties faced by the teachers at the time of using assessment and giving feedback in classrooms. The researcher also tries to know if the classroom assessment and feedback appropriate for the learners and about the condition of the administrative and logistic supports that the institutions provide their students to enhance the English language skill.

1.4 Rationale of the Study

This study deals with an important area in the case of teaching and learning of English language. Assessment and feedback are parts and parcels of English language teaching at the undergraduate level. The ambition of this study was to explore the outlooks of the teachers and learners regarding the current status of assessment and feedback at the undergraduate level in Bangladesh. The purpose is to identify possible areas for improving

students learning rates by using new assessments. Appropriate assessment and corrective feedback are essential for effective learning. Without these, a language class is incomplete. This study is essential because, with assessment and feedback, a language class can be held effectively. These research findings will also contribute to giving correct assessment and feedback in classrooms. This study will help both teachers and students to promote their lessons. Therefore, we hope that this will make the teachers aware of the importance of assessment and feedback for the undergraduate level.

1.5 Limitations of the Study

The sample size of this study is small which has been taken from Savar Upazila in Dhaka district. It could not be possible to go outside of Savar Upazila. It could be better if the samples were chosen from diverse sources. More teachers and students from diverse groups could reflect different results for the study. There were some teachers who were afraid to tell the truth. The researcher had assured that they would not have to face any problem for that.

2. Literature review

2.1 What is Assessment?

Assessment is the process of gathering and discussing information from multiple and diverse sources in order to develop a deep understanding of what students know, understand, and can do with their knowledge as a result of their educational experiences; the process culminates when assessment results are used to improve subsequent learning (Huba & Freed, 2000). Assessment involves the use of empirical data on student learning to refine programs and improve student learning (Allen, 2004). Erwin (1991) considers assessment as the systematic basis for making inferences about the learning and development of students. Erwin further maintains it as the process of defining, selecting, designing, collecting, analyzing, interpreting, and using the information to increase students' learning and development. Assessment is the systematic collection, review, and use of information about educational programs undertaken for the purpose of improving student learning and development (Palomba & Banta, 1999).

2.2 What is Feedback?

Feedback is any kind of information that learners receive about their performance. This can be corrective feedback which focuses a learner's attention on errors, or it can be non-corrective, in the form of praise or encouragement, for example. However, the feedback can also be about the performance of peers. In fact, some learners benefit more from hearing this kind of feedback than feedback which concerns them more directly (Havranek, 2002: 259). It is also useful to bear in mind that feedback does not only go to the learner: it can also go to the teacher. A student's performance in a communicative speaking task is a rich source of information about the teacher's teaching (Hattie & Timperley, 2007). In a fluency-based task, it is often the things that students did not say that provide the richest feedback to teachers. It is these gaps that can suggest the features of language that a teacher may wish to provide feedback on, especially in delayed feedback. Definition of feedback by Ramaprasad (1983): "Feedback is information about the gap between the actual level and the reference level of a system parameter which is used to alter the gap in some way" (1983). Sadler (1989, p. 77) argues that formative assessment is "specifically intended to provide feedback on performance to improve and accelerate learning." Explaining the student with a grade or marker when responding to a piece of assessment work is not, without a general idea, providing an answer. Similarly, making comments about a student's

work is not wrong, giving feedback. Feedback is a word that needs careful explanation to represent a contribution to learning.

2.3 Background of Classroom-based Assessment

The incorporation of classroom assessment techniques is a concept that has been used by teachers for many years. Whether a teacher is using a learned strategy in training, or an integrated strategy alone, teachers should know that their methods are effective and many feel that the desire to understand students' understanding makes sense. Despite this innate characteristic among teachers, the first real attempt to document such techniques for teachers didn't appear until 1988, when K. Patricia Cross and Thomas A. Angelo published entitled, *Classroom Assessment Techniques: A Handbook for Faculty*. Language learning is concerned with developing certain skills that are developed and perfected through practice. The English curriculum prescribed different aspects of the English Language teaching-learning process. Assessment is one of the important aspects which is being treated as a teaching-learning process as well (Stiggins, 1991). Assessing students is a very important part of a teacher's teaching (Nitko, 1996). It is an integrated process for determining the nature and extent of students' learning and achievement (Linn & Gronland, 2005). There are two types of assessment in general, formative assessment and summative assessment (Ahsan, 2009). The current English curriculum (NCTB, 1995) especially focuses on the summative assessment through terminal examinations. Less importance has been given to formative assessment. Recently from 2007 a new dimension in assessment, namely School-Based Assessment (SBA), has been introduced in national assessment procedures (Begum & Farooqui, 2008).

2.4 Types of Assessment

(a) Formative Assessment

Formative assessment is seen by Black & Wiliam (1998a) as at the heart of effective teaching - an essential feature for good teaching as well as efficient learning. It is a form of assessment to help students develop as learners and teachers develop as teachers to both produce effective learning. In their seminal review paper, Black & Wiliam (1998a) provide a commonly used definition of formative assessment as: "encompassing all those activities undertaken by teachers, and/or by their students, which provide information to be used as feedback to modify the teaching and learning activities in which they are engaged". (Black & Wiliam 1998a, p. 7-8) The central role of formative assessment in teaching and learning in Higher Education is also espoused by Juwah et al (2004)⁴. As a process for providing information to teachers about the difficulties students may be experiencing so they can refocus their teaching efforts, the authors argue that formative assessment "should be an integral part of teaching and learning in HE" (Juwah 2004 et al, p. 3).

(b) Summative Assessment

When constructing summative assessments, (Stiggins, 2001) recommends that teachers keep the perspective that the real users of assessment data are the students themselves. Merely receiving a letter or numerical grade advises a student of the value placed on the work, but it does not do anything to clarify the learning that has—or has not—taken place. That is, what questions were answered correctly? Which were incorrect? Assuming that the information was taught because it bears some importance, what does the student still need to learn? Keeping the focus on students and learning as assessments are designed represents the first step toward high-quality assessments. So, while formative assessments are specifically intended to inform the teacher, summative assessments must also communicate effectively with the test taker. Summative assessment is used to quantify achievement, to reward achievement, to provide data for selection (to the next stage in

education or to employment). For all these reasons the validity and reliability of summative assessment are of the greatest importance. A summative assessment can provide information that has diagnostic value.

2.5 Assessment and Feedback in Bangladesh

British educational method has been followed in Bangladesh for many years without considering the actual circumstance. There are three systems as primary, secondary and tertiary level in Bangladesh. At the end of the secondary level, students move to the next phase – the higher secondary level than the undergraduate level. The English Curriculum and Textbooks are provided by the National Curriculum and Textbook Board (NCTB) for the students of class one to twelve. English 1st and 2nd papers are provided to the students as their textbook. Some major developments took place in the 1990s to improve English language teaching and learning.

The study findings will be helpful to understand the nature and practice of current classroom assessment and feedback in English classes at the undergraduate level in Bangladesh. The study finding will identify the strengths and weaknesses of the application of assessment and feedback in English classes at the undergraduate level in Bangladesh. The large classroom is one of the key problems for Bangladeshi learners to get appropriate feedback. Regarding the number of students in the language classroom, Sinha (2001) has said, "In a language classroom, we need a limited number of students" (p.173). But, in reality, nearly all English classrooms in the public sectors in Bangladesh are overcrowded and often have as many as 200 students in them (Siddique, 2004, p.3). At present, the system of assessment and feedback at the undergraduate level in Bangladesh is not well decorated. The authority and the teachers of educational institutions should reshape the method of assessment and feedback to lift the quality of education and knowledge of students. The syllabuses and curriculums of undergraduate levels of Bangladesh should be reorganized within a short time to compete with neighboring countries.

3. Methodology

3.1 Design of the Study

This study is an attempt to use different assessments and feedback at the undergraduate level in Bangladeshi classrooms. With a view to finding out the problems, this research paper has been conducted through a questionnaire survey including teachers and students. The researcher has visited different Universities and colleges to collect the data. The research finds different types of assessment and feedback in the case of English language teaching in Bangladesh. It is quantitative in nature. Questionnaires are provided among the students' and teachers' for collecting the data. The questions are multiple choices. In both cases settings are formal.

3.2 Sampling

The study is conducted at Savar Upazila in Dhaka district. The data has been collected from four different public, national, and private universities at Savar Upazila in Dhaka district. These are Jahanagirnagar University, Savar Govt. College, City University and Daffodil International University. The participants are randomly chosen from universities. The total number of these participants is 200 and the total number of teachers is 20. The sample size of the study is limited due to time and cost constraints.

3.3 Research Instruments

Several research instruments have been used to analyze data. The researcher has used a questionnaire method for the students and for the teachers as the instrument for collecting

data. In order to find the answers to the questions, data has been collected using the questionnaire technique. Questionnaires are distributed among the students and the teachers in order to know the actual scenario of teaching and learning of English language in case of the undergraduate level in Bangladesh. The researcher has prepared the questionnaire with the help of his supervisor.

3.3.1 Nonparticipant Observation

In this study, the researcher plays his role as a non-participant observer in the data collection process. As a nonparticipant, the observer does not participate directly in the activities being observed. It is distinguished from participant observation by the observer's level and kind of involvement in the research setting, the non participant observer adopting a more distant and separate role.

3.3.2 Survey

Teachers' and students' survey through questionnaire methodology is used in this research. It has a number of advantages as it makes the result quantifiable and interpretable. Within a short period of time respondents can fill up a questionnaire form. Answers found from the questionnaire procedure are easy to analyze and appropriate, to sum up in a conclusion more easily. Seliger and Shohamy (1989, p.172) have stated a number of advantages of using a questionnaire for data collection. It provides more uniform and standard data that is expected from subjects as all subjects are given the same questionnaire. Because of anonymity, it also helps subjects to feel more relaxed to share information. Thus, the data is collected more accurately in the questionnaire.

3.3.2.1 Students' Questionnaire

In the students' questionnaire, there are 20 multiple choice questions for each. Every multiple-choice question has 5 options.

3.3.2.2 Teachers' Questionnaire

In teachers' questionnaire, there are 20 multiple choice questions for each. The data has been collected from their respective Universities.

Always	Sometimes	Neutral	Seldom	Never
1	2	3	4	5

Five-point Likert scales are used:

4. Findings and Data Analysis

4.1 Data Analysis of Students' Questionnaire

Table-1: Percentage of Students' response to the questionnaire

	Questions	(a)Always	(b)Sometimes	(c)Neutral	(d)Seldom	(e)Never
1	Do you get enough feedback from your teacher?	50%	25%	10%	10%	5%
2	Do you get appropriate assessments in your classroom?	60%	20%	5%	10%	5%
3	Are the teachers co-operative and friendly with you in the classroom?	40%	20%	20%	10%	15%
4	Do you get the right feedback in your classroom?	40%	10%	15%	15%	20%
5	Do you get any difficulties in the assessment?	45%	25%	15%	10%	5%
6	Do you think that the assessments which are provided in the class are authentic?	50%	10%	20%	5%	15%
7	Do you follow classroom assessment?	55%	20%	5%	15%	5%
8	Do you understand your teacher's lectures?	55%	15%	10%	5%	15%
9	Do you think such kinds of assessments are difficult?	40%	30%	10%	15%	5%
10	Are you satisfied with your teachers' performance?	50%	15%	5%	10%	20%
11	Do you follow classroom feedback in your study?	60%	15%	15%	10%	0%
12	Do you submit your problems to your teachers in order to correct them?	40%	20%	20%	15%	5%
13	Do you get the appropriate answer from your teacher?	60%	20%	5%	10%	5%
14	Do your teachers follow any plan to improve classroom tasks?	35%	15%	25%	20%	5%
15	Do your teachers supervise and check your written script?	60%	25%	5%	10%	0%
16	Do Assessments and feedback help you to progress your knowledge?	75%	10%	5%	10%	0%
17	Do your teachers follow formative assessments in the classroom?	55%	20%	5%	10%	10%
18	Do your teachers evaluate summative assessment correctly?	50%	20%	15%	10%	5%

19	Do you ask questions to your teachers if you do not understand anything?	60%	20%	5%	10%	5%
20	Do you find any difficulty in classroom feedback?	45%	20%	15%	20%	0%

Source: Survey conducted by the researcher

4.2 Data Analysis of Teachers' Questionnaire

Table-2: Percentage of Teachers' response to the questionnaire

SL NO.	Questions	Results				
		(a)Always	(b)Sometimes	(c)Neutral	(d)Seldom	(e)Never
1	Do you give feedback in your class?	55%	15%	20%	5%	5%
2	Does your institution provide essential materials for the students?	60%	10%	10%	15%	5%
3	Do you feel comfortable giving feedback to the students?	75%	10%	5%	5%	5%
4	Do you use a multimedia projector to provide feedback in your class?	20%	15%	35%	5%	25%
5	Do you follow any technique to run your class?	50%	10%	20%	10%	10%
6	Do you face any problems in your class?	55%	15%	15%	10%	5%
7	Are you interested in giving feedback in class?	65%	15%	15%	5%	0%
8	Do you get enough responses from your students?	45%	20%	0%	15%	20%
9	Is formative assessment helpful for the students?	75%	5%	10%	5%	5%
10	Does authority arrange a training program for the teacher?	40%	5%	10%	10%	35%
11	Do you provide an appropriate assessment in your class?	60%	10%	20%	10%	0%
12	Are the assessments beneficial for the	75%	15%	5%	5%	0%

	students?					
13	Do you think that such kind of assessments helps the students?	60%	20%	5%	10%	5%
14	Do you attempt to provide authentic assessment to the students?	55%	15%	20%	5%	5%
15	Are the students co-operative in the class?	50%	10%	5%	10%	25%
6	Do the assessments fulfill students' needs?	65%	10%	5%	10%	10%
17	Do you attach new assessment for the students?	30%	15%	20%	10%	25%
18	Do you think that assessment and feedback are provided properly?	45%	20%	5%	15%	15%
19	Do you work to improve students' proficiency?	45%	5%	25%	10%	15%
20	Do you pay heedfully in your class?	70%	10%	10%	10%	0%

Source: Survey conducted by the researcher

Response Analysis of Teacher Questionnaire

In reply to the first question, the researcher finds that most of the teachers that are 55% always give corrective feedback in their class. It is very helpful for the students to develop their skills. The findings also show that 15% of teachers sometimes, 20% of teachers neutral and 5% are seldom as well as 5% of teachers never give corrective feedback in their class. In response to the second question, it is found that 60% of institutions provide essential materials for the students to enhance their English language skills. It is very important for the learners to carry on their studies accurately. It has also been seen that 10% of institutions sometimes, 10% institutions neutral and 15% institution seldom provide materials to the learners. It is also seen that 5% of institutions never provide essential materials for the students. Question no. three provides data that 55% of teachers feel comfort to give feedback to their students in their class and 15% of teachers feel comfort sometimes in class. It is also exhibited that 25% of teachers are neutral that means they do not give any comment on the question. It is also shown that 5% of teachers feel comfortable seldom and 0% never feel comfortable. In reply to the fourth question, the researcher finds that 20% of teachers use multimedia projectors to give corrective feedback in their class. It is very supportive for the students to develop their proficiency. The finding also shows that 15% of teachers sometimes use a multimedia projector, 20% teachers are neutral and 5% teachers are seldom as well as 5% teachers never use it to give corrective feedback in their class. In response to the fifth question, the finding shows that 50% of teachers follow new techniques to run their classes to promote students' knowledge. It is also seen that 10% of teachers use sometimes and 20% remain neutral in this question. It is further exhibited that 10% of teachers follow seldom and 10% never use it. From question no. six, it is found that 55% of teachers face problems in their classroom while they usually take a class. It has also been seen that 15% of teachers face sometimes, 15% are neutral and 10% are seldom facing problems. It is also seen that 5% of teachers

never face problems in their classrooms. Question no. seven shows that 65% of teachers are interested to give feedback in their classroom. It is also found that 15% of teachers are interested sometimes and 10% remain neutral that means they have no comment on this question. It is also seen that 5% are seldom interested and 5% of teachers never interested to give feedback in their class. Question no. eight illustrates that 45% of teachers get enough responses from their students. It also shows that 20% of teachers get enough response and 0% is neutral as well as 15% think that they get seldom. 20% of teachers do not get any response from their students. In response to question no. nine, the researcher finds that 75% of teachers think that formative assessments are helpful for their students. It is also seen that 5% of teachers believe this and 10% are neutral. 5% of teachers seldom think and 5% never think that formative assessments are helpful for the students. Question no. ten shows that only 40% of authorities arrange training programs for their teachers. 5% of authorities sometimes and 10% remain neutral. It is also seen that 10% arrange seldom and 35% never arrange a training program for their teachers.

In response to question no. 11, the researchers found that 60% of teachers provide appropriate assessments in their class. 10% provide sometimes and 20% remain neutral. It is also seen that 10% of teachers provide seldom and 0% never provide appropriate assessment in their class. In question no. 12, it is exhibited that 75% of teachers think that assessments that are provided by the authority to students are beneficial for the students. 15% think sometimes and 5% are neutral as well as 5% think seldom. 0% think that assessments are not beneficial for the students. In question no.13, it is found that 60% of teachers think that such assessments are helpful for the students. On the contrary, in question no.14, it is exhibited that 55% of teachers attempt to provide authentic assessment to the students. In case of question no. 15, it is found that 50% of students are co-operative and 25% of students are not co-cooperative. In question no.16, it is seen that 65% of teachers think that such kind of assessment fulfills the students' needs and 10% of teachers emphasize never. In response to question no.17, it is found that only 30% of teachers attach new assessments depending on their students' needs. 45% of teachers say that assessment and feedback are provided properly and 45% also attempt to improve students' proficiency.

5. Discussion of the findings

5.1 Discussions in Terms of Students' Perspective

From chart 1, the researcher finds that the students do not get enough feedback from their teacher. Here only 50% of students get corrective feedback from their teachers. But feedback is very important for the students to increase their proficiency level in English language. It is also seen that 5% of students never get corrective feedback at all in their classrooms. It is not a satisfactory scene in the case of an English language class where feedback is essential for all time. From the next question, it is seen that 40% of students get the right feedback but almost 100% right feedback is required for the students. After that, it is found that 45% of students give their opinion that they get difficulties in their assessments. Teachers and authorities should remove all kinds of obstacles from their students' lessons. An authentic assessment and feedback should be provided to the students as well as teachers should judge the lesson whether these are appropriate or not. It is displayed that 50% of students think that the assessments which are given to their class are authentic. Students' have also some problems that they do not follow their assessment fully at their home. Another problem is that 15% of students do not understand

their teachers' lectures at all. Since they have problems, the teachers should deliver understandable lectures in their class. In question no.7, it is seen that only 40% of students submit their problems to their teacher to solve but it should be increased gradually. From the next question, it is seen that 60% of students get an appropriate answer from their teachers. After that, it exhibited that only 35% of teachers attempt to improve classroom tasks. Actually, it is not a satisfactory rate at all to anyone because all teachers should always try to improve educational materials. In response to question no.9, the researchers found that 60% of students give their opinion that their teachers supervise and check their written script, where about 100% attention of teachers are needed. From the next question, it is found that 75% of students say that assessment and feedback help them to improve their knowledge. Then it is seen that 55% of teachers follow formative assessment in their classroom. 20, it is found that 45% of students find difficulty in classroom feedback. Any kind of difficulty should be demolished.

5.2 Discussion in Terms of Teachers' Perspective

From chart 1, it is clearly seen that 55% of teachers try to give corrective feedback in their class to make correct their students from ignorance and 5% do not give any feedback in their class. Though 5% of teachers do not give feedback, it is not acceptable at all because all teachers should give corrective feedback as far as possible. In chart 2, the researcher sees that the institutions cannot provide the supportive materials in the class for the students. 60% of institutions always provide supportive materials while 5% of institutions never provide supportive materials in the classroom. But the use of educational materials is very important in English language teaching. In chart 3, according to the teachers, most of the teachers feel comfort to give feedback to their students. Where 25% remain neutral that means they are middle of the road. In response to question no. 4, only 20% of teachers use multimedia projectors to provide feedback in their class but the multimedia projector is almost essential for teachers to cope up with the modern period. The next question shows that 50% of teachers follow some techniques to run their class and 55% of teachers face some problems in their class. In response to question no.7, it is seen that 65% of teachers interested to give feedback and 5% are not interested to give feedback at all. The following question exhibits that 45% of students give a response in the class and 20% never give any response in their class. In question 10, it is seen that only 40% of institutions arrange training programs for their teachers but it should be increased gradually to build perfect teachers for the students. On the contrary, 35% of institutions never arrange any training program for the teachers at all. This culture should be removed immediately from our country. Then it is shown that 60% of teachers are able to provide appropriate assessments with the help of authorities in their classroom. In response to question no.14, 55% of teachers attempt to provide authentic assessments to their students. 5% of teachers never provide any authentic assessment. In response to question no.15, it is found that 50% of students are co-operative and 25% of students are not co-operative. Co-operative students are essential for learning English language. In response to question no.16, it is found that 65% of teachers consider that such kind of assessment fulfills the students' needs and 10% of teachers stress on never. All institutions need to provide appropriate assessments so that students can fulfill their requirements. In response to question no.17, it is discovered that only 30% of teachers put together new assessments depending on their students' wants. 45% of teachers declare that assessment and feedback are provided correctly and 45% also attempt to improve students' skills. In response to the question no.20, it is seen that 70% of teachers pay attention fully in their class, 10% sometimes, 10% neutral, and 10% seldom as well as 0% not at all pay attention

to their class and students. Teacher's attention, labor, and positive outlook are essential for students.

5.3 Discussion in Terms of Research Questions

The research questions of this study intend to find out the difficulties faced by the teachers at the time of using assessment and giving feedback in the classroom. The researcher also tries to know if the classroom assessment and feedback appropriate for the learners and about the condition of the administrative and logistic supports that the institutions provide their students to enhance the English language skill.

The findings of the study seem to suggest that teachers and authorities should include important assessments to enhance the learning rate of learners. Corrective feedback is also needed in case of teaching English language at the undergraduate level in Bangladesh. The difficulties encountered by the teachers are lack of motivation, confidence, students' poor knowledge of English language, lack of infrastructural support, lack of training, lack of initiative for the continuous development of English language teaching and handling large classes within the limited class duration, etc. The students also face many problems such as hesitation, nervousness, vocabulary and grammar and so on. They also do not get any proper scope to learn and to interact with their learning lesson. From the findings, it is found that the classroom activities done in the classroom are not appropriate for teaching and learning English language. The classroom is teachers centered rather than student-centered where real-life activities, assessment, and feedback, as well as contextualized materials, are hardly used. So, the students do not get enough scope for group discussion, role play, presentation, etc. to develop their English language skills. From the results, it is clear that the institutions cannot provide logistic support in a proper way to develop the English language teaching system for the teachers. So, the teachers and the students feel the necessity of the administrative and logistic support from the institutions to enhance the teaching and learning of English language.

6. Conclusion and Suggestion

6.1 Conclusion

This research has helped to raise the vital issues related to the development of English language teaching at the undergraduate level in Bangladesh. The present study has identified some old ways of using assessment and feedback as well as some new approach which are helpful for learning English language. The study has also discovered the need for teachers' training, the necessity of modern technology, interaction with the students, teaching techniques, etc. This study has also explored the assessment and feedback which are practiced in many ways. Findings of the study show that assessment and feedback are the undividable part of classroom practice but assessment and feedback practiced in the classroom were not up to the mark. One of the reasons for this was that both English teachers and the authority did not have enough knowledge about the English curriculum. For assessment purposes, teachers mostly asked questions for assessing students' understanding and most of the questions were taken from multiple choice questions which were asked from the lowest level of the cognitive domain. Students answered those questions using one or two words and those questions did not provide students any scope to imagine critically. Students showed diverse views about different assessment practices. They preferred verbal assessment more because of its legality. They argued, in oral assessment nobody can copy, whereas in written assessment there is scope to copy from others. It discovered that assessment is a shared practice of classroom where both students

and teacher participated as well as they judge the assessment process. In addition, feedback practiced in the classroom was not at a satisfactory level. As from different studies assessment and feedback, practices have been identified as very effective and inseparable. The findings of this study suggest that the activities are not sufficient to make the students skilled in English language because these are conducted by using inappropriate methodologies and materials are hardly used. They encounter different problems like handling large classes within the limited class duration, lack of training lack of suitable materials. On the basis of the research evidence, it can be concluded that effective assessments and feedback will gradually help learners to improve their English proficiency.

6.2 Summary of the Findings

From the above findings, lack of proper environment, inappropriate use of assessment and uncooperative surroundings are some of the critical problems. Teachers face difficulties in managing classroom which is the result of defective curriculum and lack of training. Students are reluctant and less confident in receiving feedback. Some other drawbacks are found like the influence of traditional learning systems, insufficient teaching aids, inappropriate use of technology and defective teaching method hamper in achieving the goal.

6.3 Suggestions

Assessments and feedback are part and parcel of language class because, without these, language is not possible. In order to make the classroom more effective, it is necessary for the teachers to be careful about their assessments and feedback. By the mutual participation and co-operation of the teachers, learners and the concerned authorities, we will be able to overcome the referred problems and reach the goal of English language proficiency. Based on the findings of the study the most important recommendations are teachers' implementation of new methods and assessment as well as feedback to enhance learner's skills in English language and students' motivation to be heedful in the classroom so that educational purposes will be accomplished. The teacher should correct the students in a very positive way and should not try to blame the students; every student has a different way of learning. Learners' motivation is the most important thing for the language classroom and the lesson should be selected based on learners' needs as well. The number of students in each class should be kept limited where teachers would be able to handle the students' problems with precision. The authorities of the schools should pay special attention to provide all the logistic support (multimedia classroom, language lab self-access center, etc.) to improve students' proficiency. Teachers also need to check up their students' scripts attentively. Students should follow classroom assessment and feedback to correct them. Cooperation between students and teachers is needed for a language class. All should pay heedfully in their classroom and they should attempt to improve their assessments.

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